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FROM THESIS TO STUDIO: THE USE OF DOCTORAL RESEARCH TO SUPPORT INDUSTRIAL DESIGN PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

The vocational nature of design education requires students to be exposed to tools and methods that have been validated through use by practitioners during professional practice. However, there is also an opportunity and a need for academic research to be more pro-active in both the evaluation of emerging tools and development of new resources. This paper discusses two case studies in which PhD research was used to inform educational practice in industrial design education. The first case study, supported by Hewlett Packard USA, evaluated the use of the Tablet PC as a mobile design studio that could integrate sketching with other core design activities. The second, supported by the Industrial Designers Society of America, developed a compact card-based tool (iD Cards) to support understanding and communication in the use of design representations during new product development. The paper discusses the methods used in the research and identifies the positive contribution to student learning.

Keywords: Design tools, PhD, industrial design

INTRODUCTION

The vocational nature of design education requires universities and colleges to equip students with the knowledge and skills required to engage in professional practice. At undergraduate and taught masters level, there is a fundamental need to identify how designers practice and to translate this into an appropriate curriculum for student designers. This reactive approach is typical of taught courses, with pro-active opportunities to explore future curriculum content being more appropriate for

investigation through academic research and, in particular, research degrees.

This paper explores the capacity of PhD research to inform design education through the evaluation and evolution of tools that are central to industrial design practice. Case study methods (Birley and Moreland, 1998; Moore 1983) are used to describe two projects that received the support of a technology developer and a professional body that resulted in valuable insights and material for curriculum development. The methodologies for each case study will now be discussed.

CASE STUDY 1: THE USE OF THE TABLET PC AS A MOBILE DESIGN STUDIO

The tower and lap-top PC play a central role in industrial design activity during New Product Development (NPD), having particular relevance during the phases of design activity that require greater control over form and detail such as design development and specification. However, the creative generation of ideas at the front end of industrial design practice is particularly well suited to manual sketching which facilitates the required level of spontaneity and ambiguity. Whilst it is possible to employ sketching hardware for this activity, such as an interactive tablet (e.g. Wacom Cintiq), these are relatively large and when combined with the required PC lack the portability and spontaneity afforded by a sketch pad.

Comparative studies of digital and paper-based sketching studies are limited, with Faber's small-scale comparison on the experiences of students in creative disciplines other than industrial design being an exception (Faber 2009). In 2009, the author received an Innovation in Education Grant from Hewlett Packard USA. The aim of this three year

research project was to explore the capabilities of the Tablet PC to facilitate a totally digital strategy for New Product Development (NPD), with a specific focus on the inclusion of creative concept generation through sketching. The distinctive feature of the Tablet PC is its ability to reverse the position of the screen so that it can be viewed in what would normally be the closed lap-top position. The screen can be used with a dedicated pen-type stylus which has the capacity for freehand sketching. This sketching functionality is additional to the other computer-based activities that are central to industrial design practice, such as 3D Computer Aided Design (CAD) and image manipulation.

RESEARCH METHODS

The application for the Grant utilised findings from an on-going PhD by Noor Al-Doy and, when awarded, it enabled the researcher to exploit the resource within their methodology. The first phase of the research, that took place over one year, was to gather feedback on the capability of the Tablet PC to be used by final year industrial/product design students as a highly portable yet capable digital design studio. Sixteen finalist students were provided with a Tablet PC and, in addition to MS Office, received software to support industrial design activity, i.e. high-end CAD (Pro-Engineer), sketching (SketchBook Pro) and image manipulation (Photoshop). From the 16 students that participated in the study, 7 were studying for a BA in Industrial Design, 7 for a BSc in Product Design and 2 were studying for a B/Eng in Product Design and Manufacture. During their studies, all students had been taught how to sketch 3D product form to support industrial design activity.

The students received the Tablet PCs in the October of the 2009/10 academic year and had full use whilst undertaking design activity for their major projects and supporting modules. On-going support was provided by the author (responsible for teaching design sketching) plus a research assistant and in November 2009, the students participated in a two hour 'Shared Experiences' session during which they were able to discuss the benefits and challenges afforded by the Tablet PC and problems they were having were addressed.

After using the Tablet PCs for design activity for four months, data collection commenced through the following activities:

- Design Exercise and Product Sketching Exercise (January 2010)
- Expert Opinion on Sketching Questionnaire (February 2010)
- Focus Groups (February 2010)
- Closing Session (June 2010)

The specific data collection activities will now be discussed.

The Design Exercise and Product Sketching Exercise were undertaken to collect data on student attitudes towards the use of the Tablet PC, with expert opinion being collected on the sketched output. The design exercise allocated 2 hours for the design of a new product (a pepper mill) using the Tablet PC only. During the design exercise, students employed the full functionality of the Tablet PC's interactive screen during sketching activity, including use of the virtual keyboard when the physical keyboard was hidden under the screen (see Figure 1) and capacity to loosely apply tone and colour (see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Use of the virtual keyboard whilst sketching

Figure 2. Loose application of colour whilst sketching

The students were given a detailed briefing on what was required for the pepper mill design which was supported by 50 examples of existing products as photographs. The format required for the outcome of this exercise was typical of that for the concept generation stage of new product development i.e. a single perspective view of the proposal plus elevational views. The application of colour/shade was optional and the use of 3D computer aided design software was not allowed i.e. it had to be sketched using the interactive tablet only. At the end of the design exercise, the proposals were collected using a memory stick for future analysis. An example of a design proposal completed in 90 minutes of design activity can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example of sketch rendered output from design exercise

During observations, it was noted that students were rapidly switching between design sketching and accessing supporting material on the internet. Whilst such activity would be possible when using a computer and paper-based techniques, it was apparent that the Tablet PC facilitated a seamless transition between sketching and access to on-line images to support design activity. This went beyond the more typical searches for examples of related products and stylistic direction, as was the case with the proposal illustrated in Figure 3 where the student accessed an image of hands in the pose required for the visualisation. This was imported into the image manipulation software and traced for use in the proposal.

The pepper mill design exercise was undertaken to help develop capability in use of the interactive screen. The exercise was supported by the author and researcher assistant and was an opportunity for the students to address problems and share expertise. It also provided an indication of progress in the development of design capability as the students had previously provided examples of their work before being given a Tablet PC.

On completion of the pepper mill design exercise, the students completed a Design Exercise Questionnaire that required them to list three strengths and three weaknesses in using the Tablet PC for the task. Results from the design exercise questionnaire indicated that the Tablet PC supported improvements in sketching capability through the capacity to delete unwanted line/colour and then redo it. This enabled the students to be more fluid in the way that they worked due to the potential for immediate corrections. Although the students did not move around the room with the Tablet PC during the pepper mill design exercise, having been using it for over four months, they noted its portability and capacity for them to undertake digital sketching 'on the move' e.g. on trains or during visits to friends/relatives. In contrast, the key negative response was that the digital sketching techniques were more difficult to learn than non-digital techniques. This response had significant implications for learning support if the Tablet PC was to be introduced into the industrial design curriculum.

In addition to the design exercise, a product sketching exercise was undertaken to identify changes in sketching capability arising from the use of the Tablet PC. This required students to sketch contrasting products using both paper-based methods and the Tablet PC, with the process being recorded on video for future analysis (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Use of video to capture sketching activity

Product sketching typically employs techniques that are appropriate to the required 3D form, with crating and ellipses being used for forms with a high degree of primitive geometry; and contour lines and bulkheads for those with more organic form. For this reason, the students were required to sketch from observation, a battery operated torch that was based entirely on primitives (see Figure 5) and a child's spoon that had organic form (see Figure 6).

Figure 5. Geometric torch used for product sketching exercise

Figure 6. Organic form of spoon used for product sketching exercise

By requiring students to sketch the two very different forms, differences in outcomes from use of the Tablet PC and paper-based methods would be evident. Five minutes was allowed for each product sketch with each being undertaken using digital and paper-based methods. This resulted in the production of four sketches for each student: 2 x torch sketches (one using the Tablet PC and the other paper-based techniques); 2 x spoon sketches (one using the Tablet PC and the other paper-based techniques). The sequence of undertaking the sketch exercises was randomised to avoid order effects.

On completion of the sketching exercises, students were asked to complete a Product Sketching Questionnaire that focused on the contrasting experiences afforded through use of the two media. The first question explored the students' perception of their sketching capability when using the two media. The second question requested open-ended responses to ways in which the product sketching strategies differed between paper-based techniques and the Tablet PC by requiring a list in rank order with a maximum of 5 responses. The final question sought opinion on a series of statements that might apply to either product sketching using paper-based techniques or the Tablet PC. The results from the sketching exercise indicated that students felt that their ability to sketch using non-digital methods was greater than when using digital methods, although it was acknowledged that they had been using non-digital methods since their first year of studies. During the sketching exercise, students identified the capability of the software to allow them to work on layers as a significant advantage, especially when employing colour and tone.

In addition to feedback from the students on their experience of using the Tablet PC and paper-based sketching during the product sketching exercise, expert opinion was gathered on the effectiveness of the students' sketches to represent product form. An Expert Opinion on Sketching Questionnaire utilised the sketches produced by individual students, pairing them for each product and presenting them as full size images on an A4 sheet. Tick boxes were added to enable an expert on sketching to indicate which of the two sketches most accurately represented product form or if no difference in the two could not be identified. An example of the A4 questionnaire sheet for the spoon can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Sample question from the Expert Opinion Questionnaire for the digital and non-digital spoon sketches

The questionnaire was completed by eight academics with responsibility for teaching product sketching to undergraduate students. They were also qualified industrial/product designers with a minimum of ten year's commercial experience. The academics were provided with photographs of the torch and spoon and asked to complete the questionnaire by making a judgement on which was the most successful sketch in terms of line and perspective for the spoon and torch, although they were unaware of the specific media used. If no clear difference between the two sketches could be identified, the respondents had the option of ticking a "similar" box. The students

were not required to apply colour or tone and if used this was ignored in the judgement.

The number of questionnaire responses was relatively low but, as experts in sketching, there was a high degree of reliability in the responses. The results from the academics indicated that the non-digital sketches were superior to the digital sketches which confirmed the student perception from the Student Sketching Questionnaire.

After using the Tablet PCs for four months, the students participated in a focus group during which seven semi-structured questions were used to elicit open-ended feedback on their general experience of sketching with the Tablet PC; its impact on sketching, creativity and productivity; what skills the students thought were required to teach the use of the Tablet PC; if they felt that the Tablet PC should be introduced to all industrial/product design students; and any other comments on the use of the Tablet PC. The two focus groups of 8 students each were facilitated by the author who had experience of professional practice, teaching product sketching and digital design methods.

72 distinctive responses were recorded and translated into a final questionnaire for use when the students returned the computers at the end of the academic year. The open nature of the focus groups provided a forum in which the widest possible range of issues could be elicited. This supported the aim of the final Use of Tablet PC Questionnaire which was to identify the significance of the wide range of issues raised in the focus group. The results indicated that the students had an overwhelmingly positive attitude to the role of the Tablet PC to support their development as industrial designers, even though they appeared to be more capable at sketching when using paper-based techniques. Key reasons for the more general positive response to the Tablet PC were its portability; capacity to effectively explore alternative solutions; its contribution to collaboration (sharing digital images); and that it increased the potential to design products entirely digitally. The key negative feature of the Tablet PC was that digital sketching was more difficult to learn than paper-based techniques.

The research provided valuable insights that are being used to inform decision-making, not only in the relevance of the Tablet PC to industrial design

education, but also more generic products such as the stand-alone interactive tablet.

CASE STUDY 2: SUPPORTING UNDERSTANDING AND COMMUNICATION IN THE USE OF DESIGN REPRESENTATIONS

The use of representations for the communication of design intent are central to industrial design practice, but the development of skills and knowledge to enable students to produce the representations comprise a significant component of the undergraduate curriculum. This is very much the case for the core activities of paper-based sketching, the use of 3D CAD, digital image manipulation and model making/prototyping; where students are required to develop capability to the standard required for professional practice. Whilst there is extensive published material to support the development of specific techniques and, in particular, sketching and drawing, information on the full range of representations and context of use remains limited. This shortfall in teaching material was addressed using a combination of data collected during a Loughborough Design School PhD by Eujin Pei and post-doctoral development to produce a card-based design tool (iD Cards) that was designed and then distributed to students, educators and novice practitioners around the world. However, the research that led to this outcome commenced with a somewhat different aim; to enhance the collaboration between industrial designers and engineering designers.

RESEARCH METHODS

The starting point for the development of the iD Cards was a Loughborough Design School PhD that was supervised by the author and awarded to Eujin Pei in 2009 (Pei, 2009). The PhD investigated the barriers to effective collaboration between industrial designers and engineering designers, with problems in the use and knowledge of design representations being identified as a significant issue and one that had the potential to be addressed through doctoral research.

The literature review for the PhD indicated that, in an increasingly competitive commercial environment, organisations were under constant pressure to identify and implement efficiency gains.

In terms of the interaction between industrial designers and engineering designers, the problematic nature of the collaboration between the two disciplines is acknowledged (Jevnaker, 1998; Persson and Warell 2003). The Loughborough Design School PhD identified three distinct problem categories: conflicts in values and principles; differences in design representation; and education differences.

The research established that industrial designers tended to operate with open-ended, ill-defined problems; while engineering designers had a much more focused and objective approach. These dissimilar approaches could, at times, generate conflict (Persson and Warell, 2003). In addition to fundamental differences in approaches (Cross, 1985), another key barrier was that industrial designers focused on appearance and user-interface, whereas engineering designers focused on functionality and manufacturing detail (Kim, et al., 2006). The engineering designer produced detail drawings and CAD geometry for the manufacture of a working product based on quality, performance and cost (Flurschein, 1983). In contrast, industrial designers produced representations such as rendered sketches and appearance models.

Effective communication is essential when undertaking new product development and Clark and Wheelwright (1993) note the importance of this in achieving cohesion and efficiency. Studies indicated that engineering designers struggled to fully understand the vocabulary used by industrial designers but, in contrast, Fiske (1998) identified that industrial designers found it difficult to understand engineering design-related issues such as technical specifications. In addition, words may not have the same meaning for all members of a design team, with Persson and Warell (2003) acknowledging that communication becomes more effective once the team develops a common vocabulary through and understanding of communicative codes and language, e.g. symbols, product reproductions and message content.

Erhorn and Stark (1994) note that because the various participants in new product development have their own vocabulary that is suited to specific activities, there can be difficulty in communicating and understanding amongst those outside the specific professional group. Although the language

may be similar, identical words have been found to have different meanings (Ashford 1969).

As part of the PhD, an empirical study was undertaken with the aim of identifying and resolving barriers to effective collaboration between industrial designers and engineering designers during new product development. The first data collection event involved a ten week study that was undertaken with 17 design consultancies specialising in electronic consumer products. The subjects were qualified industrial designers and engineering designers with varying levels of experience. The fieldwork consisted of 45 hours of in-depth interviews and 80 hours of observations. The empirical studies utilised a qualitative research methodology, incorporating semi-structured interviews and the observation of participants during a commercial project.

The interviews allowed respondents to fully describe their personal experiences relating to group interaction; reasons for project success and failure; and methods used during the project. To increase reliability, a mix of large, medium and small companies with an equal number of industrial designers and engineering designers participated in the survey. The data was coded into a spreadsheet which identified 61 problem categories. A coding and clustering technique was then used to condense the results into a matrix using recurrence and importance.

The matrix highlighted the 19 most frequently occurring problems (occurring 3 or more times) which were then categorised under the following headings:

- **Problem Category A - Conflict in values and principles**
Engineering designers tend to work with quantified solutions with a focus on efficiency. Industrial designers favoured an open-ended approach with less constrained solutions
- **Problem Category B - Differences in design representation**
A lack of a common understanding/language for both disciplines represented a significant obstacle to effective collaboration
- **Problem Category C - Education differences**
Differences in education resulted in different capabilities, approaches and expectations

Observations were used to obtain detailed information during a 2 week case study that involved the commercial design of an electronic communication device that required collaboration between industrial designers and engineering designers within a design consultancy. Analysis of the results identified that a lack of a common language in design representations made it more difficult for industrial designers and engineering designers to understand and empathise with each other.

A representation is defined as a model of the object it symbolises (Palmer, 1987). Internal representations encompass imagery and cognitive activity, with external representations being visual or verbal (Goel, 1995) and expressed through language, graphics or actual objects. The research project had a focus on external representations that included physical and digital formats. In the early stages of design activity, when a solution is ill defined, more unstructured representations, such as sketches, are employed. According to Tang (1991), sketching allows visualisation, communication and information storage; while Larkin and Simon (1987) point out that representations can externalise and visualise problems as they emerge. Other studies highlight the importance of product representations in enhancing team communication (Ulrich and Eppinger 1995) and as a thinking tool (Ferguson, 1992). Suwa et al (1998) note that sketches provide visual cues for further work and for the construction of 'functional thoughts'.

The potentially ill defined nature of sketches can lead to them being interpreted differently by industrial designers and engineering designers, but this ambiguity also enables industrial designers to re-interpret them and gain new insights (Goel, 1995). While engineering designers employ formal systems, such as ISO standards, industrial designers have been cited as using less established representation types and ones that are ill-defined and imprecise (Saddler, 2001). In highlighting the differences in the vocabulary of each discipline, Smith (1997) suggests the use of a common understanding of shared definitions.

In developing a tool to promote shared understanding, the PhD research sought to provide definitions for the key design representations used by industrial designers and engineering designers;

when they were used; and to identify the key types of design and technical information that they were used to communicate. Numerous formats for the emerging tool were evaluated and a physical card format was selected on the basis of portability and convenience.

The cards were developed as sets of red cards for industrial designers and blue cards for engineering designers, with the content for each set being divided into 3 sections. The red and blue sets differed in the fact that the popularity of use for the design representations was not the same for industrial designers and engineering designers as evident through the data on use that was collected via the interviews. Section 1 of the cards identified the key design stages of the new product development process (concept design, design development, embodiment design, specification). The front face provided a definition of a specific design stage, with 4 cards being used to indicate the popularity of use of representations during each of 4 stages with the most popular appearing at the top. Section 2 described the key design and technical information used by industrial designers and engineering designers in the design process. The front face had a definition of the type of design or technical information, with the reverse showing the popularity of specific representations to communicate the design or technical information. Section 3 identified the 34 most significant design representations used by industrial designers and engineering designers during the design process. The front face gave a definition of the design representation and the reverse face showed the design/technical information that was embodied in the representation plus the popularity of the representation when used during a specific design stage. An example of a card from the information section for industrial designers can be seen in Figure 8 and for engineering designers in Figure 9.

The card-based tool, called “CoLab”, was validated through semi-structured interviews with participants from 15 design companies and academic institutions. The results indicated that most respondents felt that the tool would provide a common ground in design representations that would contribute to enhanced collaboration. There was also a 3-week case study during which the cards were

used for a live, client-based project. The case study approach allowed data to be collected within a real-life context (Yin, 1989) with observations being conducted in a natural work environment. A design diary captured the activities, enabling later analysis.

Figure 8. Front and reverse of design information card for design intent in industrial designers' (red) set

Figure 9. Front and reverse of design information card for design intent in engineering designers' (blue) set

The case study confirmed the relevance of the design representations used on the cards along with the use of the design/technical information. It was noted that both industrial designers and engineering designers used identical keywords picked up from the cards during discussions which helped reduce the potential for misunderstanding. The case study provided further positive feedback which reinforced the capacity of the cards to facilitate collaboration in a multi-disciplinary environment.

Having received significant support for the CoLab design tool from participants in the data collection process, on completion of the PhD, attempts were made to put the product into production. Despite meetings with several major stakeholders in new product development, the cost of the 114 full colour double sided cards was identified as a significant obstacle to commercialisation. Whilst the potential existed to convert the physical CoLab system into a web-based tool, this was resisted on the grounds of an overwhelmingly positive response to the convenience and portability of physical cards. During a search for viable alternatives to a playing card-type product, the commercially available 'Z-Card' fold-out printing format was identified as a potential solution as it was available in a variety of sizes and aspect ratios. Unfortunately, although the Z-Card product was cost effective, the format was not suitable for the creation of 114 double-sided as used on the CoLab tool.

During a review of the potential for the Z-Card format to be used as an alternative to the 114 double-sided cards, considerable interest in the

CoLab tool was shown following a presentation at the 2009 Industrial Designers Society of America International Conference in Miami. Its contribution to support student and novice designers was particularly well received. Ensuing discussions resulted in the potential to produce a design tool that included the full range of design representations but also employed empirical data on their use by industrial designers in terms of when they were used during product development and for what types of information. Significant development work was undertaken to redesign the CoLab tool for the Z-Card format which was re-branded 'iD Cards'. The iD Cards had credit card-size front and rear covers that were printed on card, with the fold-out panels being on paper. Yellow tabs indicated at which stage of product development the design representations were used, with tabs to indicate if they were used to communicate design information (red tabs) of engineering information (blue tabs). The folded iD Card is shown in Figure 10, with the folded-out front sheet in Figure 11 and reverse in Figure 12.

Figure 10. Folded iD Cards

Figure 11. Folded out front sheet for ID Cards

Figure 12. Folded out rear sheet for ID Cards

The collaboration with the Industrial Designers Society of America (IDSA) facilitated the printing and distribution of the iD Cards in the UK and USA, with the potential to access a modified PDF via a link on the web site for the Design Practice Research Group at Loughborough University (www.lboro.ac.uk/departments/lds/research/groups/design-practice/). To support design education in the UK, an iD Card was sent to the Design and Technology department of every secondary school in the UK (total 5002) and 5000 were distributed to students and practitioners in the USA by the IDSA in April 2011. The iD Cards were also selected by the IDSA as a finalist in the 2011 International Design Excellence Awards (IDEA).

CONCLUSIONS

The two case studies have discussed contrasting strategies in which academic design research can inform design education. Manufacturers can make significant claims about the contribution of their products to design practice, but objective evaluation using academic research has the capacity to provide impartial feedback. Whilst it must be acknowledged that there is significant cost associated with the Tablet PC, it has been identified as an effective means of integrating sketching with the more established digital design techniques of 3D CAD and web browsing. It was of some significance that the methods used during sketching with the Tablet PC were above and beyond those available through non-digital techniques, such as the ability to edit. What might appear as a relatively simple functionality for software such as a word processing package, when integrated into sketching activity, the capacity to edit made a significant contribution to the development of capability.

In contrast to the use of design research to evaluate an emerging technology, the development of the iD Cards demonstrated how such methods can be employed to address a need for information that supports practice. The development of the tool to provide information on the use of design representations lasted for over four years, but it indicates how the original aims for research can evolve, through need and opportunity, to produce a tool that is of relevance to a related but different group, i.e. instead of focusing on the needs of

practicing industrial designers and engineering designers, it was used to support design students and novice designers.

The key feature of both case studies has been the contribution of key stakeholders in both activities where Hewlett Packard and the IDSA were central to the research. In fact, the research would not have been viable without their support. It must be acknowledged that the availability of such support to evaluate and develop design tools is relatively rare, with research funding, particularly in the UK, focusing on multi-disciplinary activity for more topical issues. However, the development of core capability in design disciplines remains of considerable significance to academics in the field and these case studies demonstrate the value and impact of research to education and, ultimately, commercial effectiveness.

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